

Gold nanoparticles on silica monospheres modified by amino groups

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keywords

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abstract

Silica monospheres with a diameter of 330 nm modified with aminosilane compounds of three different basicities have been prepared. Surface coverage of the silica with an organic compound leads to an increase of the point of zero charge (PZC) of the silica surface from 2.1 to 5.1, 6.5 and 7.2 values, depending on the amine used. From these silicas, gold-containing catalysts have been prepared by a deposition-precipitation method at the same pH as the PZC of the support. The best results have been obtained using 3-(Diethoxymethylsilyl) propylamine as a modifying agent, which has allowed obtaining a good dispersion of the gold particles with an average size of 3.8 nm.

1. Introduction

In the last years the number of works related to the use of supported gold catalysts increased exponentially, due to the high activity of gold in a large number of catalytic processes, especially oxidation reactions [1–6]. The catalytic activity of these systems is determined by the state of oxidation, the size of the gold particles and the redox properties of the support, although the discussion still remains open for several determinant aspects of these factors, such as the nature of the active sites of gold and the reaction mechanisms. The majority of the investigated supports are reducible metal oxides (Fe₂O₃, TiO₂, CeO₂, etc.), which have been described as the more appropriate ones [5–7]. Non-reducible supports, such as Al₂O₃ and SiO₂, have been considered as less active systems in which the catalytic behaviour is a function essentially of the size of the gold particles: the higher activity is obtained for smaller particles. Nevertheless, the interest in these systems is based on the possibility to elucidate the role of the metal itself, since the weak interaction between the gold particles and the support surface minimizes the interaction effect. The catalytic behaviour also depends on other important factors such as the geometric and electronic structure of the gold particles [8]. The preparation of highly dispersed Au/Al₂O₃ catalysts has been described widely in the scientific literature and does not propose major difficulties, since methods commonly used for the synthesis of gold systems,

such as deposition-precipitation, co-precipitation and impregnation have been developed [2,6,9–11]. However, these methods have not been effective to obtain highly dispersed nanosize gold particles on SiO₂. The difficulty is related to the specific conditions of the deposition of gold. Due to the low value of the point of zero charge (PZC) of SiO₂ (close to 2), the surface of the silica is charged negatively at a pH higher than that value, making it very difficult for interaction and deposition of the gold anions (for instance [AuCl₄]⁻ that comes from the chloroauric acid (HAuCl₄) used as a gold precursor). To overcome the disadvantage of depositing negatively charged solution species on negatively charged silica surface, some authors propose the use of cationic species of gold, such as [Au(en)₂]³⁺ or [Au(PPh₃)₃] [12–14] or other methods of deposition, like sonochemical reduction [15], or other ones that do not include liquid solutions, e.g. chemical vapour deposition [16]. Recently other authors found it possible to prepare metal particles highly dispersed in mesoporous silica of SBA-15 type by functionalizing SBA-15 with a cationic organosilane [17]. This allowed generating a monolayer of positively charged groups on the pore surface of the material and, subsequently, incorporation of the [AuCl₄]⁻ species in the channels of the mesoporous structure by ion exchange.

The aim of the present work is to study the possibility of obtaining gold nanoparticles well dispersed on the surface of SiO₂ spheres by a standard deposition-precipitation method. The strategy of the synthesis is based on the surface modification of spherical silica particles by functionalization with organic aminosilane compounds with basic properties. This results in alteration of the point zero charge (PZC) of silica up to values higher than five. This allows formation of positive charged monolayer and reaching of pH values similar to PZC of the modified silica surface which deter-

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Fig. 1. Scanning electron micrographs (SEM) of the silica and silica modified spheres: (A) SiO₂; (B) SiO₂-PAN; (C) SiO₂-DEM; (D) SiO₂-MAP.

Fig. 2. Difference DRIFTS spectra obtained by rationing to the DRIFTS spectrum of the parent silica spheres collected “in situ” at 100 °C under a nitrogen flow. The DRIFTS spectrum of the corresponding modified silica is obtained under the same conditions: (a) Au/SiO₂-DEM; (b) Au/SiO₂-MAP and (c) Au/SiO₂-PAN.

mines the success of the deposition–precipitation process. The choice of the monodispersed SiO₂ spheres as a supporting material is based on their ability to facilitate the deposition of the gold particles, their potential applications in optics and biotechnology

Table 1
Textural properties and of the parent and modified silica

Silica	Aminosilane	S _{BET} (m ² /g)	PZC
SiO ₂	–	12.7	2.1
SiO ₂ -PAN	PANTMS	10.6	5.1
SiO ₂ -DEM	DEMSPA	8.9	6.5
SiO ₂ -MAP	MAPTMS	8.5	7.2

[18,19], as well as the growing interest in these materials as model systems in several fields [20,21].

2. Experimental

2.1. Syntheses

2.1.1. Silica support

A batch of 20 g of monodispersed spherical silica particles were prepared following the method proposed at first by Stöber et al. [20] and then modified by Giesche [21]. Tetraethylorthosilicate (TEOS, 99% pure, Alfa), absolute ethanol (Prolabo), ammonia (25%, Panreac) and deionised water were used as reagents. The synthesis proceeded as follows. Mixture A (154.66 ml H₂O, 48.02 ml NH₃, 197.32 ml C₂H₅OH) and Mixture B (72.1 ml TEOS, 327.48 ml C₂H₅OH) were heated separately under continuous stirring for 30 min at 40 °C. Then mixture B was added to mixture A quickly and kept under vigorous stirring for 1 h. After that, the solution became milky due to the precipitation of the silica. The solid was separated by centrifugation at 8000 rpm and washed four times with deionised water and ethanol. The obtained solid was dried overnight at 60 °C and finally calcined for 2 h at 200 °C.

2.1.2. Modified silica supports

[3-(Methylamino)propyl] trimethoxysilane (MAPTMS, Fluka 97% purum grade), [3-(Phenylamino)propyl] trimethoxysilane (PANTMS, Fluka 95% technical grade) and 3-(Diethoxymethylsilyl) propylamine (DEMSPA, Aldrich 97% pure) were used as a source of amino groups for functionalizing the silica support. The method used for the incorporation of the aminopropyl groups was based on that reported by Cauvel et al. [22]. Silica was freshly activated by heating for 2 h at 110–120 °C under continuous stirring. After that, 50 ml of a 0.1 M solution of the corresponding amino source in toluene was added, and kept for 24 h under refluxing. Then,

Table 2

Textural properties, chemical composition and gold particle size (calculated from TEM observations) of the catalyst

Catalyst	Aminosilane	S_{BET} (m ² /g)	Au (wt. %)	pH of DP process	Average size of Au particle (nm)
Au/SiO ₂ -PAN	PANTMS	11.1	0.53	5.1	>60
Au/SiO ₂ -DEM	DEMSPA	8.4	0.45	6.5	3.8
Au/SiO ₂ -MAP	MAPTMS	11.2	0.18	7.2	7.2

Fig. 3. Experimentally obtained gold loadings depending on the pH during synthesis.

Fig. 4. X-ray diffraction patterns of gold modified silica: (a) Au/SiO₂-PAN; (b) Au/SiO₂-DEM and (c) Au/SiO₂-MAP.

the obtained solid was filtered, washed with toluene, and finally dried overnight at 80 °C. These materials are designated as SiO₂-PAN, SiO₂-DEM and SiO₂-MAP, depending on the compound used for functionalization of the silica.

2.1.3. Gold catalysts

Gold catalysts were synthesised by deposition-precipitation. The adequate amount of HAuCl₄ · 3H₂O (Alfa, 99.99% pure) to obtain 0.5 wt.% gold, was dissolved in the corresponding volume of deionised water to have a 10⁻³ M concentration. After that, the pH of the solution was adjusted to the value of the Z-point of the support by addition of NaOH 0.1 M. Then, the support was added and kept under continuous stirring for one night. If necessary, the pH of the solution was re-adjusted during this period of time, in order to have the requested constant pH value. The samples obtained were

washed with distilled water several times (until disappearance of Cl⁻ and Na⁺), and dried overnight at 100 °C in an oven.

2.2. Characterization techniques

The gold content of the samples was determined by X-ray fluorescence spectrometry (XRF) in a Siemens SRS 3000 sequential spectrophotometer with a rhodium tube as the source of radiation. XRF measurements were performed onto pressed pellets (sample included in 10 wt% of wax).

X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis was performed on a Siemens diffractometer D500. Diffraction patterns were recorded with Cu Kα radiation (40 mA, 40 kV) over a 2θ-range of 10° to 70° and a position-sensitive detector using a step size of 0.05° and a step time of 1 s.

The point of zero charge (PZC) of the support was determined by measuring (Malven Zetamaster) electrophoretic mobilities of aqueous dispersions as a function of pH, at constant ionic strength (10⁻² mol dm⁻³ NaCl). The pH was varied by adding HCl or NaOH, as needed.

The textural properties were studied by N₂ adsorption measurements at liquid nitrogen temperature. The experiments were carried out in a micromeritics ASAP 2010 equipment. Before analysis, the samples were degassed for 2 h at 150 °C in vacuum.

Scanning electron micrographs (SEM) were taken using a JEOL JSM-5400 electron microprobe and Link energy dispersive X-ray (EDX) analyser.

Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) observations were carried out in a Philips CM200 microscope operating at 200 kV. The samples were dispersed in ethanol by sonication and dropped on a copper grid coated with a carbon film.

Diffuse reflectance infrared fourier transform spectroscopy (DRIFTS) measurements were obtained in a Thermo Nicolet Nexus IR spectrometer with KBr optics and a MCT/B detector, in which an environmental cell (Spectra-Tech 0030-103) equipped with ZnS windows was coupled. The samples were placed without packing or dilution, heated from room temperature to 100 °C in a flow of N₂ at 50 ml min⁻¹, and spectra (64 scans, 4 cm⁻¹ of resolution) were obtained after 1 h at this temperature. The spectra of unmodified silica support obtained under the same conditions, were used as background.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Silica modified supports

The XRD patterns of the modified silicas are typical of amorphous solids, without peaks assignable to any crystalline phase. The SEM images (Fig. 1) of the silica and the modified silicas are too similar and show homogeneous and monodispersed distribution of SiO₂ spheres with a diameter of 330 nm approximately.

Fig. 2 shows the 4000–2500 cm⁻¹ region of the difference DRIFTS spectra obtained by ratioing of the DRIFTS spectrum of the parent silica spheres and the DRIFTS spectrum of the corresponding modified silica. All the spectra have been collected in situ after 1 h at 100 °C under nitrogen flow, in order to dehydrate the samples. Positive bands at 2963, 2927 and 2857 cm⁻¹

and negative ones at 3740 and 3225 cm^{-1} are clearly observed. Bands at 2800–3000 cm^{-1} can be attributed to the stretching vibrations of C–H bonds in organic molecules [23,24]. In fact, bands at 2927 and 2857 cm^{-1} have been described as C–H stretching bands characteristic of aminopropyl groups incorporated into the channels of mesoporous SBA-15 silica molecular sieves [25]. The band at 3740 cm^{-1} is assigned to the symmetrical stretching mode of O–H from isolated terminal Si–OH groups [23,25] and that at 3225 cm^{-1} can be attributed to N–H stretching vibrations of a surface complex remaining on the silica surface after synthesis [23]. These results indicate that the synthesis of the modified silica sup-

port has been successful. The functionalization was obtained by a surface modification with different precursors of amino groups. The silanol (Si–OH) and surface N–H groups remaining on the surface of the silica spheres are the sites for incorporation of the aminosilane compounds, being consumed in this process (negative DRIFTS bands), resulting in the aminosilane compound chemically bonded on the silica surface. Neither the size, nor the morphology of the silica spheres was affected in this process.

Nevertheless, the acid–basic properties of the surface as well as the specific BET area of the silica spheres, were affected by the modification as presented in Table 1. On the contrary, insignificant

Fig. 5. Transmission electron micrographs (TEM) and particle size distribution of the gold in the catalysts: (A) Au/SiO₂-MAP; (B) Au/SiO₂-DEM and (C) Au/SiO₂-PAN.

changes of the textural properties of silica, such as specific surface or volume and pore diameter were observed. On the other hand, depending on the basicity of the aminosilane used, an increase of the surface basicity (PZC point) of silica up to 7.2 was observed, which is appropriate for an effective deposition of gold by the deposition-precipitation method.

3.2. Gold catalysts

Table 2 presents the specific BET surface area of the gold-containing catalysts. The results show that the process of gold deposition hardly affects the initial specific surface values of the modified silica used as a support.

However, the experimentally obtained gold loadings are different for all catalysts. The most significant difference between the measured (0.18 wt.%) and the target (0.5 wt.%) gold loading was observed with the Au/SiO₂-MAP sample. This difference should be related to the pH values at which the gold deposition was carried out: 5.1, 6.5 and 7.2 for Au/SiO₂-PAN, Au/SiO₂-DEM and Au/SiO₂-MAP, respectively. In fact, a relation between the pH values and the gold loadings achieved is observed, in such a way that the lower the pH, the higher the amount of gold incorporated into the solid (Fig. 3). Hence, it seems that low pH values would favour the precipitation of gold. The strong influence of the experimental parameters of the deposition-precipitation procedure (pH, temperature, volume of chloroauric solution and time of contact between the support and the gold solution, etc.) as well as of the changes in the surface area, structure or crystalline phases of the support, in the gold uptake has been well established [26–28]. Our results indicate that the enhancement of the surface basicity of the silica is not related to the higher precipitation of gold. However, as it will be shown below, this is necessary for obtaining high dispersion of gold.

The XRD patterns of the catalysts prepared (Fig. 4) do not show any peaks assignable to gold species, which is in accordance with the low gold loadings (0.5 wt.%) and/or the small gold particle size achieved.

Notwithstanding the low loadings of gold and the fact that it was impossible to detect by XRD, the TEM analysis was very informative. The images of the different supported gold catalysts are presented in Fig. 5.

TEM micrographs of the Au/SiO₂-PAN sample clearly show that the deposition of the gold particles has not been effective, although, according to the X-ray fluorescence analysis, this is the sample with the highest amount of Au. In this catalyst only very big particles (>60 nm) were detected; which in some cases formed agglomerations, clearly precipitated in the solution and not on the surface of the support. In this case, the deposition-precipitation process was performed at pH 5.1 and the deposition of gold was not effective. This is in general agreement with data from the literature [1–4] describing the impossibility of obtaining supported gold nanoparticles from the chloroauric acid at pH of 5 or lower.

For the other two samples (Au/SiO₂-DEM and Au/SiO₂-MAP) the deposition was performed at higher pH values, 6.5 and 7.2, respectively, and the size of the gold nanoparticles deposited was smaller. Moreover, gold is located on the external surface of the SiO₂ spheres. The average values of the gold particles are presented in Table 2, whereas the distribution of sizes is shown in the histogram in Fig. 5. In the Au/SiO₂-MAP sample, a relatively small number of gold particles were detected, which is in accordance with the low loading (0.18%), with sizes ranging between 1 and 20 nm and an average particle size of 7.2 nm. The Au/SiO₂-DEM sample contains a larger number of gold particles and the average size is of 3.8 nm (a considerable number of particles are smaller than 2 nm). It is noteworthy that in the samples with well dispersed gold nanoparticles (Au/SiO₂-MAP and Au/SiO₂-DEM) partial fusion between the

spheres of silica is observed, indicating a surface interaction between the aminosilane species. This was not observed with the Au/SiO₂-PAN catalyst.

The results show that the nature of the aminosilane used to modify silica surface is decisive for the size and distribution of the gold nanoparticles. It seems that for obtaining of highly dispersed gold a pH value above 5 is necessary. However, the particle size distribution evidently depends on the chemical composition of the modifier, since the best gold dispersion was observed with the Au/SiO₂-DEM sample prepared at pH of 6.5.

4. Conclusions

We have shown that it is possible to prepare gold catalysts supported on SiO₂ spheres by a deposition-precipitation method using the [AuCl₄]⁻ anion as a gold precursor. This can be achieved via preliminary modification of the silica surface by covering with basic aminosilane compounds. By this strategy it is possible to obtain a good dispersion of the gold particles. The best results correspond to synthesis by a deposition-precipitation method at pH 6.5, when a gold particle size of 3.8 nm is reached. At pH values close to 5, the gold precipitates out of the surface of the spheres, generate big agglomerations of metallic particles, while at pH of 7.2 the gold amount incorporated is much lower than the target gold loading.

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